

Evolving a Business Excellence Model Based On Sustainable Human Capital Resources for Mauritius: A Qualitative Approach

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Abstract—this paper is part of a doctoral research work conducted to identify a proper business excellence model for Mauritius. As it involves a deep probe into the human aspect of an enterprise a qualitative approach has been used to obtain insights of the model to be used. The stakeholders are people involved in the business excellence award competition. The study has yielded the business excellence model based on sustainable human capital resources, keeping in view the triple bottom line aspects of the enterprise namely economic, social and environmental as well as other major aspects of leadership strategy, operations, marketing, information management and results. Such original insights will be useful for academicians, enterprises and scholars of business excellence. All the criteria for a good qualitative work has been observed,

Key words—Business Excellence, human resources, sustainability,

1. Introduction

The world is constantly changing and with the advancement in technology, the trade liberalisation policy of WTO bringing down the barriers to international trade and converting the world into a global village, the pace is becoming more pronounced. Survival in this environment calls for more vigilance, creation, innovation and a constant eye on the gear of competitiveness. Many business paradigms are being questioned. Mauritius, like many countries, has also questioned its business excellence model. The whole effectiveness of the MBEA was being questioned. Such questioning is not only crucial for the custodians, it is also important for the Government, the support institutions and more importantly for the businesses. They require guidance on which model to follow. The MBEA model is not effective if major constraints are not addressed. Indeed, it is observed that the blooming of the local Mauritian business landscape to the excellence level was impeded by indigenous fundamental problems, like lack of finance and insufficient infrastructure, but the main one being non-availability of manpower for further development and a general lack of motivation and belongingness to the enterprise. This bears heavily on the competitiveness of enterprises. Mauritius being a small island state with limited resources, the problem takes more significant proportions.

Nowadays, for many modern thinkers, “sustainability” and more precisely *sustainable human capital resources* (Barney, 1991) has become a prerequisite for the perennial success of an enterprise. The concept “sustainability” has become important, if not crucial. The concept sustainability as defined by the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED, 1987) was originally meant for the protection of the environment. However, the concept is being used in all other aspects of life including the management of an enterprise.

The main concerns of enterprises are to carve out a model that will result into satisfying all its stakeholders, preserve the profitability of the enterprise in the short term as well as in the long term, thus maintaining its sustainability. Several researchers have adopted different approaches to looking at this issue. Ardichvili (2012) and Freeman (1983) have advocated that sustainability of human resources to the business is essential. For them, traditional human resources management has to be revisited and the human sustainability aspect be seriously considered. Talwar (2009) presented a new approach based on human values. He proved that those aspects coming from the Vedic teachings (Talwar 2008) are crucial to preserving the sustainability of an enterprise. Confucius (Gallagher & Raric, 2001), Younis (2009) and Vivekananda (Ranganathanada, 1989) have stressed the importance of human values and spiritualism in business management.

The above approaches have never been used to investigate the appropriateness of the BE model used for Mauritius using the sustainable human capital resources (SHCR) approach.

2. Literature review

Definition of Business Excellence

Business Excellence models are used worldwide by enterprises for self-assessing themselves, benchmark with others, especially competitors, and adopt best business practices to emulate good performing ones to improve the level of their enterprises. Several academics have provided different definitions and frameworks regarding the BE concept. One of the most revered definitions is that of the European Foundation for Quality Management (EFQM), which defines ‘Excellence’ (whether it be organisational or business excellence) as the “outstanding practice in managing the organisation and achieving results, all based on a set of eight fundamental concepts” and its framework will “guide your organisation towards achieving success exist in various forms across the world” (EFQM, 2012.)

Overview of important Business Excellence Models

The Deming Management Method (DMM) of improving quality was developed by the US Scientist W. Edward Deming, based on the experience he gained in teaching the use of statistical techniques for monitoring and improving industrial processes to top managers, engineers and floor workers in the Japanese manufacturing industry. Subsequently, the Japanese introduced the “Deming Prize”, the first globally known business excellence model in 1951 to honour Dr. Deming. Malcolm Baldrige Model and Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award

The Malcolm Baldrige model is recognised as the best-known excellence model in the world. It is the pillar of most of the models used in the world. The Malcolm Baldrige National Quality Award introduced in the USA in 1987, is designed “*to help organizational processes, capabilities and results, facilitate the communication and sharing of best practices and serve as a working tool for understanding and managing organizational performance.*” (NIST, 2015).

The Australian Business Excellence Framework (ABEF) (SAI Global, 2010) was developed in 1987 and was inspired by other leading international models such as the EFQM Excellence Model, Baldrige Performance Excellence Criteria, and the Singapore Quality Criteria.

Models contributing to sustainable capital resources aspects

One of the important models is that of Michael Porter (1985). The industry –based view of a competitive strategy of a firm is attributable to the seminal work of Porter (1985). Barney (1991) regards Porter’s work, which is based on the theories of industrial organization (I-O) economics, as the single most “influential contribution” to the field of strategic management. According to Porter (1985, p3), the competitive advantage firm gains over its competitors is primarily the “*value it creates for its buyers in excess of the firm’s cost of creating it*”.

Barney (1991) developed the resource-based –view (RBV) to compensate for the absence of an indication of the use of resources in the Porter’s model. In his model for analyzing the potential of several firm resources for generating sustained

competitive advantage, he identified four empirical indicators, namely *valuable resources*, rare resources, imperfectly imitable resources and no *substitutability (VRIS)*.

According to Elkington (1997), sustainable business is the new managerial paradigm for the next century. According to him, a business is sustainable when it lives up to the “triple bottom line” of economic prosperity, environmental quality, and social justice. The three dimensions of the “triple bottom line” are interrelated and to be able to achieve them, he said that the business requires a revolution of thinking and acting in no less than seven dimensions known as the 7D’s which are; markets, values, transparency, life-cycle technology, partnership, time-perspective and corporate governance.

Wyne Mc Phee (2014) developed a new sustainability model for the firm. Wyne Mc Phee has used Porter’s Value Chain as a base wherein he has added the dimension of sustaining activities like people, relationship, systems, ideas and infrastructure, factors which are not directly linked to the product life cycle but can create value directly by value creation. Mc Phee created an important concept on how he sees sustainability of a firm in the long run: for him a firm’s situation (Value) in the long run will depend on its Margin (profit) and the Reputation it creates.

Thom, Zaugg and Blum (2001) developed a model wherein they identified three pillars responsible for sustainable human resources management. The three pillars are *work –*

Paul Gollan (2006) presented a model depicting major factors which influence and are the outcome of HR sustainability namely *employee consultation and involvement, organisational change, work-life balance, career development & organisational learning, workplace institutions & systems.*

The Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) (Cavagnaro and Curiel 2012) provides a better insight of the behaviour of an individual, in this case within the firm. According to the TPB, an individual’s behaviour is the result of his/her intention to perform that behaviour which in turn is influenced by three factors namely; *the individual’s attitude towards the behaviour, subjective norms* (perceived social pressure to perform or not to perform the behaviour) and *perceived behavioural control*. An important aspect to be understood among people in an enterprise is the human need. Maslow has been able to define the human need namely the “physiological need”, “safety” need, Social need and *self-actualisation*.

The Three Levels of Sustainability (TLS) framework of Cavagnaro and Curiel (2012) forms the backbone of the expected sustainable framework that emerges from the various literatures.

The ISO 26000 (2010) Framework goes a little further that the other models and covers implementation as well. The ISO 26000 (2010) Framework not only shows how to ensure the balance of profits, people and planet but suggest ways to execute and attain these balances. ISO 26000 (2010) is a crucial add-on that guarantees the successful realisation of a sustainable human resource BE model.

3. Methodology

The qualitative investigation is meant to give an insightful view on the necessity of having a BE model which is based on sustainable human capital resources. Enterprises, top personalities and trade unionists, 16 in Table 1 all form part of the stakeholders that will provide this framework. This qualitative exercise has adopted both the phenomenology and the grounded theory approach as a theoretical framework is derived ultimately given that the various constructs have to be theoretically sound. According to Lincoln and Guba (1985), the four criteria for evaluating an interpretive research work are credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability. These aspects have been kept in view with recorded interviews, labeled transcripts and consent forms

4. Findings

The texts in the transcripts were then coded with the use of Nvivo 11. The questions put to the companies were about *what they think should be done over and above the usual business practices (the criteria used for MBEA) to remain excellent especially in relation to their human capital*. The individuals were asked questions according to their personal experience to gain more insight. Their replies are given below. The codes will be expressed in italics with inverted commas.

4.1 Co Aas

Co Aas which is a 15 years old garment making company owned by Mrs. C is a past Winner of MBEA in the Small category. Five codes have been created. The procedure how the themes SHCR and sub-themes have been obtained is explained below.

In Figure 1, as it will be the case for the other stakeholders, the name of the company appears on the page logo . On the left of the page logo are the circles which represent the codes created from the transcript and which have arrows labelled *codes* pointing to the page logo. These (circles) codes are placed vertically to the left of the page logo. On the left of the codes column, the themes that have been identified are those 6 constructs identified in the Literature Review namely **SHCR** which comprises *Economic, Social, and Environmental* aspects at *Enterprise* level, *Economic, Social and Environmental* aspects at *Individual* level, **Leadership, Strategy, Operations, Customers, Information Management**. The **Results** aspects are included in the constructs themselves. The arrows that link the Themes to the Codes are labeled *Child*. SHCR which includes the three aspects economic, social and environmental at individual and enterprise level will be in the third column on the left.

The strong points noted for this company are that it is keeping its “*Workers happy*” as the salary is good ,the Director maintains a “*Family atmosphere in the enterprise*”, there is “*No labour turnover*” as most of the workers have over 10 years’ service in the company, as such they become a “*Dedicated labour*” and that (she) *the Leadership* is always “*Enthusiastic*”. These words (in italics) become the five nodes created. The node “*Workers happy*” is the result of the good

Figure 1: Nvivo codes for Co Aas

salary paid to them by the enterprise and good salary when viewed in the triple bottom line aspect of the company falls under the Economic aspect. Since it is a general practice of the company it is considered to be taken at the Enterprise level. That is why it has been coded “*Workers happy*” under the theme *Economic Enterprise* which obviously comes under the theme *SHCR*.

This process will be the same for all other codes and stakeholders. However as mentioned in Chapter 3, it is the researcher that will have to ensure the most important step namely the code identification.

4.2 Co Nap

Co Nap which is owned by Mr. N for more than 20 years is also a past Winner of MBEA in the Small category. The 13 codes (first column left to the logo in Figure 2) that have been extracted show that the company is strong in its Customers, Leadership and Social (Individual and Enterprise) aspects.

It is to be noted that all these codes here relate to the human aspect in the enterprise. The company keeps the “*Workers happy*” by catering for each of the social need of the workers and even provide “*Food to them on Fridays*”. Such measures will make the workers engaged and motivate them to work for the company (Gollan, 2006) and will contribute to sustaining human resources in the enterprise.

Figure 2 : Nvivo codes for Co Nap

The Leadership aspect of the company also shows intense human aspects. The owner is keen to “*Values*”, spiritual as well as human as he is a *good* practitioner of the values of Islam. Values at the level of Leadership are the backbone of the success of an enterprise. According to Cavagnaro & Curiel (2012), Confucius, Yunis and Vivekananda spirituality should permeate Leadership. This is a key hypothesis for this research. Everything starts with leadership and if leadership is not geared toward sustainability of the human resource in an enterprise, then it is bound to face difficulties and even failure. In this case, these Leadership qualities are accompanied by a constant drive for “*Innovation*” in its daily administrative tasks (E.g. payment of salary through banks), its firm objective to “*Sustain the enterprise*” in the long run to ensure succession, allows other generations to earn a living and recoup investments cost and debts.

As shown by the various codes, the enterprise displays aggressive “*Marketing*” (**Customer**) attitudes, it is not only “*Close to its clients*”, but it also offers other add-ons, is “*Proactive with its clients*”. It has a good system where it takes the “*Feedback from its clients*” seriously and keeps a good “*Historics of clients*”. To do this the enterprise not only needs good Leadership but also people in the enterprise should be able to make these happen. Without a dedicated and motivated labour (Gollan, 2006), (Maslow), (Cavagnaro & Curiel, 2012) such aggressive marketing is not possible. It is an example of the effect of sustainable human resources on Marketing.

a. Co Top

Co Top, an 18 years old company run by Mr.M, Managing Director, won the MBEA in the Small category. The company (21 codes) shows strong qualities in Leadership, Marketing, and SHCR. The company displays “*Exemplary leadership*” by observing the disciplines laid out for the company, leading by examples (punctuality etc.), maintaining good “*Business Ethic*” and “*Transparency*”, ensures a “*Good planning system*” (to avoid unnecessary overtime), it is constantly “*Reinventing*” its strategies to “*Diversify its activities*” to remain in business.

As shown in Figure 3, the interview of the Managing Director displays SHCR (economic and social both at individual and enterprises level) strengths like “*Workers involvement*”, “*Workers are happy*”, “*No exploitation of workers*”, “*Salary satisfaction and Profits sharing system*” and “*Cultural aspects of running the enterprise*”. “*Cost-effectiveness*” is found in its Operations and the company makes extensive use of “*Updated information*” coded here under Information Management.

Figure 3: Nvivo codes for Co Top

4.4 Co Int

Co Int is a 15-year-old family business in metal engineering owned by Mr. C. The company won the MBEA in the Medium category. It shows strengths (11 codes) in its Leadership, Customers, Strategy and SHCR aspects. As shown in Figure 4 the Leader who is “*Hard Working*” and a fervent defender of “*Values*” not only wishes to show the “*Integrity*” of the company but also maintains “*Good employer-employees’ relations*” and provide “*Proactive service*” to its clients.

It is “*Honest*” to its clients in its marketing (Customers) and as Strategy tries to adopt the “*crab approach*” to sustain its business.

The company shows strengths also in its SHCR (Environmental aspect) when it is building “*Reputation in the market*” and at the same time maintaining a good image of the company in the market with its “*Value in the market*”. Internally, “*the Workers are enthusiastic and happy*” to work for the company.

In all the aspects mentioned above we can see that there is the human element which is important, human resource at the level of Leadership, Strategy, as employers (getting economic, social and environmental benefits) and as workers (committed in the honesty and integrity approach of marketing of the company).

Figure 4: Nvivo codes for Co Int

4.5 Co Ust

Co Ust., a 35 years old furniture making company owned by Mr. G is a winner of the MBEA in the Medium category. Despite being a one-man show, the company displays (Figure 5) strengths (18 codes) in SHCR, Leadership and Marketing. In the SHCR construct two codes relating to “Good work culture” and “Workers Commitment” have been extracted showing the good Environment (Individual) it is providing to each worker. The enterprise is also keeping “Good relation with the community”(Environment at Enterprise level) for example by giving them free wood and sawdust and by doing “CSR in the locality” helping people during religious festivals.

The leader of the company is dynamic “Dynamism”, knows how to lead “Exemplary leadership”, is always going forward “fonceur attitude” and has the capacity to “Innovate”. From the point of view of Marketing, the company has been able to remain in business for 35 years despite the change in technology because of its originality in “Marketing”. He has an original system of manual coding “Coding of clients” (through the different colors of pencils) for good, bad or important customers. He remains close to the requirements of his customers and is keen about their satisfaction

Figure 5: Nvivo codes for Co Ust

4.6 Co Eas

Co Eas is a 15-year-old freight company run by Mr.M which won the MBEA in the Large category. As illustrated in the 9 codes extracted in Figure 4.10, the Leadership of the company displays much enthusiasm “Enthusiastic”, he wants to lead by example “Exemplary leadership”, he is very keen about “Values”, he takes extreme care of his workers, if somebody wants some financial help the company make it possible. To maintain a sustainable human resource (Economic Enterprise) level the company is very concerned about the “Capacity Building” of its employees. Moreover, an original Social contribution at the enterprise level is that on “Saturdays children of the employees” are allowed in the office and this motivates the mothers to work. The codes extracted show the strength of the company in the SHCR and Leadership which all relate to human resources.

Figure 6: Nvivo codes for Co Eas

4.7 Co MH

Co MH is a parastatal institution which won the MBEA in the Large category. The case of Co MH is important as it shows that when people feel they have “Security of employment” they stay for a long time in the enterprise, not usually the case in other enterprises. Security of employment is an important aspect all workers are looking for as mentioned in the HRDC report (2012).

In the case of Co MH, 13 codes have been produced from areas like SHCR, Leadership, Strategy, and Customers. Though it is a semi-governmental institution, it is a special case of how to treat human capital. It is an example of security of employment which makes the workers motivated to work. Because of compulsory retirement pension, workers know that even after retirement they are guaranteed a living. They are dedicated to the company. Guaranteed retirement pension is a major shortfall flagged below by trade unions and is one of the main elements which explain why workers do not want to work in such a sector or for such a company.

At the Leadership level, the company is convinced that “Human resources “as are “important”. The codes show that at the enterprise level and individual level there are many things done to make “People Happy”, “Motivate the people” and “Look after their welfare”.

Figure 7: Nvivo codes for Co MH

4.8 MBEA Assessor-Mr B

Mr. B has been an assessor for the MBEA for three years; he is an industrial engineer and has been working mostly with SME’s. The question asked to him was what according to his experience of the MBEA, he thinks the enterprise should do to reach BE with particular reference to human capital resources. Mr. B’s reply specifically targets SME’s and his interview yielded four codes as shown in Figure 4.12. For him, SME’s have to consider “Human resources development” seriously, they have also to ensure “Capacity building”. He also mentioned that these enterprises should make considerable efforts in Marketing and that their “Internal processes” have “to be improved” drastically.

His statements are in line with what has been found in Literature Review as the four codes could fall under the themes SHCR at Economic (Enterprise and Individual) level, Customers and Operations respectively as shown in the diagram.

Figure 8: Nvivo codes for Assessor Mr B

4.9 MBEA Assessor-Ms N

Figure 9: Nvivo codes for Assessor Ms N

Ms. N has been an assessor for the MBEA for all the six years of the competition. She was former Director of the MQI and is now a private consultant in Quality systems. She was asked the same question as the other assessors and gave very insightful views on the framework to be adopted to reach BE covering the areas SHCR, Leadership, Strategy and Operations with 11 codes, as shown in Figure Table 9. For her, the “Drivers triad” are human resources, Leadership and Strategy. She is of the view that enterprises have “to Strengthen their human resources” aspects and also ensure “Succession planning” in the enterprise. At the level of Leadership in the enterprise, she invites enterprises to make use of “Framework for BE” constantly and not to abandon

them after participating in a competition. The leaders should at all cost “*Build their knowledge in risk management*”. For her there is a weakness in “*planning*” both at Strategy and Operations level. She is of the opinion that an institution similar to the MQI should be set up to cater for quality in enterprises.

4.10 MBEA Assessor-Mr. S

Mr.S has been an assessor for the MBEA for three years. He has wide experience of the weaknesses of enterprises being an auditor for ISO standards. His interview has yielded 18 codes falling under SHCR, Leadership, Customers, Operations and Strategy as seen in Figure 10.

For him, referring to “*ISO 9001 2015*” version everything starts with Leadership. The leader should “*Develop the Culture of excellence*” and “*Go for quality*”. The leaders should be able to “*Establish proper communication channels*” to allow his “*Ideas to reach the bottom line*”. The observations are in line with the elements brought up in Literature review to justify the importance of Leadership.

At the level of SHCR, he is of the view that “*Training*” should be provided to ensure “*success*” of the enterprise, “*Staff*” should be motivated by “*rewards*” and their contribution “*recognised*”. They should be covered by “*CSR*” and the leaders should ensure “*Succession planning*”.

These insights on reward and recognition are similar to what the trade unionist, Mr. C observed later as being an important element of industrial psychology and which addresses the issue of motivation of workers in Mauritius. It is in line with Maslow’s Hierarchy of Needs, namely the need for self-actualisation.

An important aspect of marketing is that nowadays it is the “*Client who judges the level of excellence*” and who “*Decides the quality of a product*”. At the level of Operation, he thinks that companies should “*Innovate to reach excellence*”. He has noticed that (with relation to Strategy), many enterprises which work as a “*team*” displays “*more creativity*” than those industrialists who works in isolation.

Figure 10: Nvivo codes for Assessor S

4.11 Mr. Ta of S Group

Mr. Ta has been for the past decades a leading figure in the Mauritius business landscape. He is Chairman of a large conglomerate, The S Group, and some time back was also associated with the R Group another large group in Mauritius. He has also been Chairman of the Jury Panel of the MBEA for two years. He was asked the question what should enterprises do to achieve BE. His reply yielded 15 codes, Figure 11, falling under Leadership, Strategy, Operations and SHCR.

For him a Leadership, should be “*Visionary*”, has a “*Long term vision*” for the enterprise, he should know that an enterprise has “*a life cycle*”, he should be “*proactive*” and be always concerned for “*Growth in his business*”.

In Strategy, besides “*Improve market*”, “*Thrust for expansion*” and ambition to “*Grow from small to large*” enterprise, he has given a very insightful idea of how to remain sustainable in business in the long run, what the researcher has called the “*Crab approach*”. Just like the crab which has many legs and moves forward with them, a business

may have at the same time many running sister companies horizontally or vertically. Within time, if one business withers away, another one may take on so that in the long run the business moves ahead and the main interest of its investors remain secure. For example, the S group some 25 years back were in many businesses. But with time they have moved and diversified into other activities and the name and the workforce is still there. In Singapore, it is tantamount to maintaining a portfolio of related businesses. This is an example of a strategy to remain sustainable, which could be followed by other investors. It also guarantees the very important aspects of security of employment for the human resources. Many people long to work for such groups.

According to Mr Ta, workers should be well paid, “*Good salary*” and they should be “*satisfied*”, this is related to the SHCR aspect. In his Group, he does not have this problem because the people are well paid. From the Operations aspect, a company should “*develop better processes*” and as mentioned above should be willing to “*Diversify its activities*”.

Figure 11: Nvivo codes for Mr. Ta

4.12 Mr.A.D of C Group

Mr.A.D is also a leading business personality in the Mauritius business landscape. He is Chairman of a large Mauritian conglomerate, the C Group. His inputs, Figure 12, have produced 8 codes which fall under SHCR, Leadership, Operations, and Customers. To better understand his views, the relevant part of his script is reproduced here. He answers the question what should the enterprise do more to achieve BE.

“We certainly believe that each manager, each leader in the row is an entrepreneur. This is key for the success of our activities. An entrepreneur is looking at the customer, customer satisfaction, is looking for new clients, innovation, is always looking at his own team, looking at cost, looking at results, accountability, this is the key aspect our company, of our culture, it’s in our DNA”.

For him Controlling cost is important as well as “*Customer Satisfaction*”. On the Leadership side, the leader should “*innovate*”, establish a system for “*Accountability*” and should be “*Results*” oriented. However, the most important statement is “*Every leader is an entrepreneur, each individual is an entrepreneur*” for the Group. This approach touches directly the human resource at all level of an enterprise, from the leadership to the worker. It is very insightful as it touches the very crucial point of motivation and engagement of the person to work for the enterprise. When the individual or the leader of the group is told to act as entrepreneur, it means that they should consider that enterprise as their own. A worker it is believed will work day and night and defy life and death to work for his own enterprise. In this case, if he considers this enterprise as his own he will give his entire best to work for the enterprise. This rejoins what the trade unionists and Assessor Mr. S said on motivating workers to work for the enterprise. The whole SCHR variable on which the researcher is investigating rest on this important aspect of motivation and engagement of the worker flagged by Mr.A.D as it involves all the stages described by Maslow’s Hierarchy of need.

Figure 12: Nvivo codes for Mr A D

4.13 Mr Bhu of C Group

Mr.Bhuanother business personality is HR Manager of C Group, another large group in Mauritius. One of the companies of the Group won the MBEA in the Large category. Mr.Bhu is quite conversant with EFQM and has been in the Group for the last 15 years. His interview covered areas like SHCR, Marketing, Leadership and Operations, as shown in Figure 13 yielding 9 codes. He was asked the question what should the enterprise do more to achieve BE.

From the Operations side, he is convinced about the “Sustainability of process and products” as he was already in the recycling of plastics. For him “Priority to Customers” should be the objective of any company. He considers “Human values” as being essential in the enterprise as his enterprise has been adopting this for the last 15 years. “Capacity building” of its workforce is also a concern for its Leadership. “You need to be profitable but you should care for your employees”: this is the inherent strength developed by the group. They “Care for employees” and are much concerned about the “triple bottom line” aspect of their human resources namely social economic and environmental. “The organization cannot live without the individual if the individual cannot perform. According to TQM if the process is good but the people are not good then we get brittle results”. This company is a vivid example of balancing profitability with care for human resources.

Figure 13: Nvivo codes for Mr Bhu

4.14 Mr.A.S from Trade Union F

Mr.A.S is a trade unionist, negotiator for Union F. He is quite active in fighting for workers in all sectors but more

particularly in the tourism sector. He has gathered more than in trade union. The question put to him was what should be done to motivate the workers to work for their enterprises. His reply yielded 8 codes from the SHCR theme, Figure 14, which is very important as insights for this study. He evoked Economic factors like the “Low salary”, “Poor working condition”, “Lack of bargaining power of workers” and most importantly workers being treated “like junk at the end of their career”. Socially, the situation is not good as the economic condition leave the worker in a situation of “no Food security”. Still, with relation to the social aspect, he is of the view that CSR should be used to palliate poverty of the human resources in the company. On the Individual’s environment side, he said that there should be green jobs and freedom of workers: having cameras at the workplace should be discouraged. For him, if these negative points are taken care of, the workers will be motivated.

Figure 14: Nvivo codes for Mr.A.S from Trade Union F

4.15 MrC from Trade Union CT

Mr. Cis a trade unionist, negotiator for the Union CT. He has more than 25 year’s experience in trade union. The interview of Mr. C has an important share in the findings of this qualitative research. The question put to him was what should be done for the workers to motivate them to work for a lifetime? His interview as shown in Figure 14 has yielded 22 codes covering areas like Leadership, Operations, Strategy and more importantly SHCR. His observation constitutes essential pillars of the sustainable human capital resource model that ultimately come out of this study. Here it would be proper to bring up some texts from the transcript itself.

According to Mr. C “About 99 % of employers think that their responsibility ends with paying salary to a worker, so long as he is employed in the enterprise. However, in our constitution, the responsibility of ensuring a salary to a worker when he goes on retirement falls on the employer. That is why there is the NPF. This means that when you are paying some worker a salary, it should include a social contribution for retirement, so that when the worker goes on retirement he can afford to

live with the pension and not return to the labour market to work again". This observation has important meaning especially with relation to people in an enterprise and their "motivation to work" for this enterprise because caring for the "worker after retirement" makes him "Happy", helps him to "feel secure" (Social contribution for retirement) after his retirement "Security after retirement" which is an important consideration for a person to engage himself with an enterprise. Lack of job security has been identified as being an important reason why people are not willing to work for an enterprise.

Moreover, as flagged by Cavagnaro & Curiel (2012), the cradle to cradle approach for a resource is the real challenge to its sustainability. When ensuring the security of a person from recruitment to retirement "Responsibility of the employer from recruitment to retirement" it will be beneficial for both the individual and the enterprise.

Another important point raised by Mr. C is "An important golden rule in industrial psychology; if you want to change the mindset of a worker to make him positive, there should be a reward". "Reward" is something which will "motivate" a worker according to Maslow. This was also mentioned by Assessor Mr. Sin in his script. "Reward to motivate the worker", "Profit sharing" and "Profit allocated for CSR for workers" are motivational factor.

"Participation of workers in enterprise decision" is another way to motivate workers to work for an enterprise. It implies also "Consultation of workers when making decision" on strategic issues for the enterprise just like in Germany. This interview has probed very deeply on the factors that can motivate workers to work for an enterprise considering at the same time the triple bottom line (economic, social and environmental) aspect at the level of the enterprise as well as at the individual level.

Figure 15: Nvivo codes for Mr.C from Trade Union CT

4.16 Mr.Ma from Apex private organisation

Mr.Ma is the present CEO of an apex private organisation regrouping several private organisations. Mr.Ma has been the mouth piece of the private sector for the last 20 years and he has a vast experience of business and business models being involved in many committees, boards, and schemes with the Government. His interview not only confirms the research gap mentioned in the Introductory Chapter but he also considers that the huge challenge of this present research is to come up with a solution to address the main problems of human resource management in Mauritius. According to him, this will be extremely helpful for the business community. To illustrate the 7 codes (Figure 15) extracted from his inputs covering areas like Strategy, Leadership, and SHCR some extract of his transcript has been brought up.

"We use to be an economy with Preference plus Low skills, for example, Cotonou, Lome etc and with WTO all preferences will go. We can no more accept to rely on low skills. This is our economic trajectory. Mauritius is caught in the trap of innovation as according to the GCR (2015-2016) we rank poorly. We have to innovate on our skills. Based on the above, most of our enterprises will have an issue of corporate reengineering and in these companies, our HR is very weak"

Mauritius has at all cost to upgrade its human resources as this is the weakness we have. For him, we have to reinvent HR and make it more suitable for the interest of business. His views are similar to those of Ardichvili (2012) cited earlier who wants to revolutionise human resources management and its teaching in universities.

According to Mr. Ma, "Nowadays the challenge in Mauritius is to make enterprise understand that they have to invest in HR, they need top guys in HR. We want to know what the profile of the top guy is in HR". This aspect will be covered in Chapter 5 of this study.

Figure 16: Nvivo codes for Mr Ma

5. Recommendations-Codes identified and Emerging model

Table 1 below above gives details of how the sustainable human resources model has been built from the open-ended interviews carried out among the main stakeholders relevant to the study. The first column lists the main constructs of the model as well as the details of the construct. The second column lists the number of sources for each of these items namely from which enterprises these nodes come from. The third column gives the number of times these nodes have come out.

For example, in the variable Social Individual of the SHCR construct the issue of "Workers happy" has been mentioned. This has been mentioned by two companies (Sources=2) Co Nap and Co Top and has been mentioned thrice (references=3). The codes are mentioned as follows:

Co Nap: Food on Friday to workers, Workers happy
Co Top: Workers happy

In this way the whole model has been constructed based on the qualitative responses of the stakeholders mentioned.

Table 1: Nodes Summary of all interviews

	S	R	Name	S	R
Sustainable human capital resources	0	0	Customers	0	0
Economic Enterprise	0	0	Build advantage on competitions	1	1
Capacity building	2	2	Client judges our level of excellence	1	2

Develop goodwill vis a vis banks	1	1	Close to clients	1	1
Efficiency of the employee depends on how much he is happy,	1	1	Coding of clients	1	1
Ensure capacity building	1	1	Credit to customers	1	1
Motivate staff with training	1	1	Customer satisfaction	1	1
No exploitation of workers	1	1	Customer who decides quality	1	1
Profit sharing	1	1	efforts in marketing	1	1
Profits sharing	1	1	Feedback from clients	1	1
Responsibility of employer recruitment to retirement	1	1	Fidelity of clients	1	1
Succession planning	1	1	Gain in quality	1	1
To ensure succession planning	1	1	Honest to clients	1	1
To strengthen human resources	1	1	Keep historic of clients	1	1
Triple bottom line	1	1	Marketing	3	5
Workers happy	1	1	New products	1	1
Economic Individual	0	0	Priority to customers	1	1
Drivers triad for BE	1	1	Proactive with clients	1	1
Each leader is an entrepreneur	1	1	Selected marketing	1	1
Employees satisfied	1	1	Information management	0	0
Good salary	1	1	Keep updated	1	1
Looking at his own people	1	1	Leadership	0	0
Low salary	1	1	Accountability	1	1
More HR development	1	1	Adapt with time	1	1
Motivate staff with rewards	1	1	Awareness of risk	1	1
No bargaining power	1	1	Build knowledge on risk management	1	1
No labour turnover	1	1	Business Ethics	1	2
Participation of workers	1	1	capacity building	1	1
Poor working condition	1	1	Capacity to lead	1	1
Profit allocated for CSR for workers	1	1	Corporate reengineering based on HR	1	1
Reward to motivate worker	1	1	Cycle of enterprise	1	1
Security of employment	1	1	Develop the culture of excellence	1	1
Train workers	1	1	Diversify activities	1	1
Training for success	1	1	Drivers triad for BE	1	1
Workers enthusiastic	1	1	Dynamism	2	3
Workers treated like junk	1	1	Each individual entrepreneur	1	1
Environmental Enterprise	0	0	Enthusiastic leadership	2	2
CSR in locality	1	1	Establish proper communication channel	1	1
Environmental dimension of sustainability	1	1	Ethics observed	1	1
Family atmosphere	1	1	Exemplary Leadership	3	6
Goodwill of company	1	1	Foncour attitude	1	1
Keep good relation with community	1	1	Go for quality	1	1
Participation of workers in enterprise decisions	1	1	Good accounting system	2	3
Profit allocated for CSR for workers	1	1	Good planning	1	1
Profit sharing	1	1	Good relation employer-employees	1	1
Reputation of company	1	1	Growth in business	1	1

Reputation on market	1	1	Hard working leadership	1	1	Enterprises based on Preference & Low skills	1	1		
Triple bottom line	1	1	Human resource important	1	1	Grow from small to large	1	1		
Value of company on the market	1	1	Idea to reach bottom line	1	1	Importance of all stakeholders	1	1		
Environmental Individual	0	0	Implementing good practices	1	1	Improve market	1	1		
Dedicated labour	1	1	Innovation	2	3	Info on competitors	1	3		
Efficiency of the employee depends on how much he is happy	1	1	Innovation always	1	1	Lack of strategic planning	1	1		
Freedom of workers	1	1	Innovation with time	1	1	Life cycle of enterprise	1	1		
Good work culture	1	1	Integrity of leader	1	1	Motivating the people	1	1		
Green jobs	1	1	ISO 9001 2015	1	1	Need for innovation	1	1		
Harmonious relation	1	1	Long term vision	1	1	Pricing Strategy	1	1		
Motivating the people	1	1	New technology	1	1	Team work more creativity	1	1		
Reward to motivate worker	1	1	Preference + Low skill	1	1	Thrust for expansion	1	1		
Staff recognition	1	1	Pressure no harmonious relations	1	1					
Workers commitment	1	1	Proactive	1	1					
Social Enterprise	0	0	Proactive service for clients	1	1					
Close to the social	1	1	Proper panning to be done	1	1					
CSR strong	1	1	Put up monitoring tools	1	1					
CSR to be used to palliate poverty	1	1	Reinvent	2	2					
Cultural aspect of running enterprise	1	1	Reinvest profits	1	1					
Donation to people	1	1	Results	2	2					
Food on Fridays	1	1	Sustain enterprise	1	1					
Human intervention related to all aspects of business	1	1	Transparent	1	1					
People happy	1	1	Values	3	3					
Profit allocated for CSR for workers	1	1	Values of leader	1	1					
Profit sharing	1	1	Visionary leader	1	1					
Saturdays children of employees	1	1	Work with framework for BE	1	1					
Social contribution for retirement	1	1	Operations	0	0					
Social dimension	1	1	Cost	1	1					
Social Individual	0	0	Cost effective	1	1					
Care for employees	1	1	Diversify activities	1	1					
CSR important	1	1	Have better processes	1	1					
Efficiency of the employee depends on how much he is happy,	1	1	Innovation and excellence	1	1					
Food security	1	1	Internal process to be improved	1	1					
Good treatment to workers	1	1	No food security	1	1					
Security after retirement	1	1	No proper planning	1	1					
Social welfare of staff	1	1	Responsibility of employer from recruitment to retirement-cradle	1	1					
Workers happy	2	3	Struggle for quality	1	1					
Workers involvement	1	1	Sustainable process& products	1	1					
Strategy	0	0								
Consultation of workers	1	1								
Crab approach	1	1								
Crab approach	1	1								
Develop competitive advantage	1	1								
Drivers triad	1	1								
Employers consult workers	1	1								

The outcomes are the elements of the model ranging from SHCR, Leadership, Strategy, Operations, Customers and Information Management (Table 1). These elements which come from the interviewees are the elements that in reality constitute the various constructs. The aspects of SHCR are very closely related to human resources. These elements explain how to sustain human resources in an enterprise. It is to be noted that some elements relate to the Process construct: e.g. *Participation of workers* and some the Results construct: e.g. *Workers satisfaction*.

Figure 17: Emerging model from all qualitative interviews
 Table 17 depicts the model that has emerged from the interviews of the various stakeholders in the qualitative investigation. It is observed that the results of the qualitative exercise confirm what has been identified in the Literature Review. These results support qualitatively that SHCR is a very important aspect of an enterprise as it permeates all aspects of the enterprise from the leader to the simple worker, from top to bottom taking economic, social and environmental dimensions.

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